

Nonlinear Mosaic Form: *Kraanerg* by Iannis Xenakis

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One of the features that distinguishes Iannis Xenakis's music is its non-teleological form. Even in *Metastaseis* (1954), an early work, there is very little in the monolithic opening to prepare for the intricate serial counterpoint of the middle section. The music proceeds by juxtaposition of contrasts or by transitions that may be sudden or more gradual. In the mid-1960s, Xenakis developed an approach to form based on the "theory of groups," by which defined states of musical entities and parameters could be combined and ordered by means of logical, mathematical operations. The result of applying this technique was a kind of "mosaic" form, where a composition's form would proceed by segments of music each delineated by the combination of parameter and/or entity states, the succession of states being logical (according to the constraints of the combinatorial rules), but nonlinear in terms of listener perception. Xenakis outlined his theory of groups in *Formalized Music*, and discussed in detail the application of the theory to *Nomos alpha* for solo cello (1966). Sketches for *Kraanerg*, a ballet for large ensemble and four-channel electroacoustic sounds (1969), indicate that Xenakis approached it in a similar fashion. *Kraanerg* is Xenakis's most ambitious work, proceeding continuously for 75 minutes. The work was commissioned for a new ballet by French choreographer Roland Petit. Sketch materials indicate that Xenakis defined the sonic entities and other musical parameters as a point of departure for the composition. This paper presents an accounting of the form of *Kraanerg* on the basis of temporal deployment of sonic entities (including silence) and other elements such as register, dynamics, timbre/instrumentation, etc.

Kraanerg, by Iannis Xenakis, was composed in 1968-69 to a commission from the National Ballet of Canada. The music, scored for 23 musicians and four-track electroacoustic tape, was intended for a new choreography by French choreographer Roland Petit. At 75 minutes in length, the work was the main event for the gala opening of the National Arts Centre in Ottawa, Canada (Harley & Harley 1997). It would turn out to be the largest work of continuous music Xenakis ever completed. In order to accomplish this task in a relatively short time (he had approximately six months to finish the score and the tape), he relied on a new compositional technique based on the "theory of groups." This was a deterministic approach to music that nonetheless produced unpredictable successions of events, resulting in nonlinear forms. *Kraanerg* can be heard as a vast mosaic of sharply defined musical segments of varying lengths, the particular sonic entities used in this piece returning over and over again, but irregularly, recombining over the course of the work's duration.

Mosaic Form *chez* Xenakis

After completing his first two major works, *Metastaseis* (1954) and *Pithoprakta* (1956), Xenakis turned his attention to theoretical matters, to the "formalization" of music. He did this first by defining what he termed the "fundamental phases of a musical work" (Xenakis 1992, 22). These phases can be summarized as follows:

1. Initial conceptions.
2. Definition of the sonic entities.
3. Definition of the transformations.
4. Microcomposition.
5. Sequential programming.
6. Implementation of calculations.
7. Final symbolic result.
8. Sonic realization.

Xenakis applied this approach to *Achorripsis* (1957) for 21 instruments. Part of his "initial conceptions" for this work was to seek "the greatest possible *asymmetry*... and the *minimum of constraints, causality, and rules*" (23). To this end, he applied stochastic procedures to a

number of aspects of the music. After defining the "sonic entities" as seven instrumental groups or playing modes (he created three string entities: arco, pizzicato, glissando), he opted to randomize the "transformations" by removing any link from one event to another. On the global level, he defined 28 sections, each lasting 15 seconds. A mean density of events per section was determined for each of the seven entities, and further stochastic procedures were applied to fix particular events within each section. Figure 1 summarizes the overall structure of *Achorripsis*, the columns representing the 28 sections, the rows representing the seven sonic entities, and the colours of each cell representing the event density for each sonic entity per section.

Figure 1. Formal outline of *Achorripsis* for 21 instruments (1957). The columns represent sections, each lasting 15 seconds, the rows represent sonic entities/instrumental groups, and the colours represent density of events within each section for each sonic entity.

The resulting form, especially when viewed as a matrix of cells as in this diagram created by the composer, resembles a mosaic.

Mosaics

In the visual domain, a mosaic is understood as a composite image made up of small pieces of marble, glass, stone, or other material. As an art form, mosaics were developed by the Greeks, achieving maturity by the 4th century B.C. This art form was taken up by the Romans, and later by Byzantium artisans. In the Islamic world, mosaics were non-representational, often evoking intricate geometric designs. Modern applications of mosaic design have used this approach to create more abstract textures (see Figure Two), in addition to images or designs. The materials themselves provide much of the "character" of such work, in addition to the way the elements are pieced together.

Figure 2. Example of mosaic art intended to create a non-figurative, abstract texture.

ST algorithm

After *Achorripsis*, Xenakis pursued his "formalization" further, succeeding by 1962 in creating a compositional algorithm written in the FORTRAN programming language. While still following his "fundamental phases," he was required to reformulate them so that they could be automated and run through a computer.

1. The work consists of a succession of sequences or movements (their durations are independent).
2. Definition of the mean density of the sounds during each sequence or movement.
3. Composition of the orchestra (sonic entities) during each sequence or movement.
4. Definition of the moments of the occurrence of each sound within each sequence or movement.
5. Attribution to each sound of an instrument drawn from the orchestra (sonic entities).
6. Attribution of a pitch as a function of the assigned instrument.
7. Attribution of a glissando speed if the sonic entity is characterized as a glissando.
8. Attribution of a duration to the sounds emitted.
9. Attribution of dynamic forms to the sounds emitted.

Of necessity, Xenakis had to be more precise and concrete in his formulation of a general compositional algorithm. It is significant that his "initial conceptions" take the form of determining a number of sequences (or movements) and their durations, along with a mean density for each. His algorithm also implies that the instrumentation will be divided into a number of groups, or sonic entities, as in *Achorripsis*. This indicates that Xenakis understood musical form as a succession of segments, contrasting in density and sonic entity. In other words, musical form can be understood as mosaic form.

Xenakis composed a family of works using his *ST* algorithm, all dating from 1962: *ST/10* for 10 instruments; *ST/4* for string quartet (an adaptation of *ST/10*); *ST/48* for orchestra; *Morsima-Amorsima* for 4 instruments; and *Atrées* for 11 instruments. articulated by the playing off of segments, sounding and silent, of changing duration.

Theory of Groups

After completing his series of algorithmic *ST* scores, Xenakis turned his attention to more deterministic approaches to music. The two main techniques he developed were based on group theory and sieve theory. It is the former that concerns us here. In the chapter of *Formalized Music*, "Towards a Philosophy of Music" (pp. 201-241), he develops the notion of "interval," common in understanding the organization of pitch, and extends this to other elements of music, such as duration, intensity, density, and degree of disorder. Given that it is possible to perceive "intervals" of musical parameters such as these, Xenakis postulates that it should be possible to treat them algebraically, to create and manipulate sets of values for each such parameter. The theory of groups provides a means to organize the succession of values for these parameters, taken as a group of linked elements. Each transformation, or succession of linked parameter values, is assigned an identity in a matrix, and the organization of this matrix determines how one transformation may succeed another (Gibson 2002).

Music composed according to such a theory would proceed by moments, each delineated by the assigned group of parameter values. Given that the values for individual elements would not necessarily change by the same "interval" as other parameters, the music would be perceived as being highly nonlinear, as each segment of the score could be highly contrasted from the previous segment, with an unpredictable, albeit mathematically logical, shuffling of the basic musical elements. the composer, resembles a mosaic.

"Group theory" compositions and synchronous works

The work that Xenakis discussed in detail in reference to his new group-theory approach to composition is *Nomos alpha* for solo cello, completed in 1966. But, even though he did not write about it in *Formalized Music*, he began applying this theory in his work *Akrata* for 16 wind instruments, completed in 1965 (Schaub 2006). Schaub, who has studied the sketch materials for this piece in the Xenakis Archives, considers that Xenakis applied these new ideas rather empirically, so that the work is not a rigorous manifestation of the theory, as is *Nomos alpha*. Xenakis does indicate that he applied group theory principles to *Nomos gamma*, a work for large, spatialized orchestra completed in 1968 (Xenakis 1992, 236-241).

The other compositions completed during the period during which Xenakis was working out his compositional principles based on group theory and sieve theory include two stage works: *Oresteia* (1966), and *Medea* (1967). The *Polytope de Montréal* (1967) is scored for four orchestral groups, but was originally presented in recorded form as part of a multimedia installation including networks of cables and hundreds of flash-bulbs programmed to create a light show in conjunction with the music. *Terretektorh* (1966) is scored for spatialized orchestra, and *Nuits* (1968) for chamber choir. None of these compositions appear to incorporate group theory principles in any substantive way, but it is certainly possible that elements of the techniques Xenakis was working out during this period appear in sections of these compositions. This is most certainly the case for *Nuits* and likely for *Terretektorh*.

Kraanerg

In the fall of 1967, Xenakis took up a position at Indiana University. His profile in North America increased considerably, with numerous guest lectures and performances. One of the higher-profile events was the choreography of his seminal orchestral works *Metasteseis* and *Pithoprakta* by famed Stravinsky collaborator, George Balanchine. The New York City Ballet premiered this new dance piece in January 1968, and it garnered critical praise. There were also other choreographies to his music appearing around that time on stages in New York, London, and Royan, France. So, in the summer of 1968, when the National Ballet of Canada and French choreographer Roland Petit were discussing possible composers for a new ballet to inaugurate the National Arts Centre in Ottawa in June 1969, Canada's capitol city, Xenakis was put forward, and he agreed to take on the project (Harley 2012).

This was a major commission: an important cultural event with the gala performance including dignitaries and press from around the world; the work itself requiring 75 minutes of music for a full-length ballet, to be scored for chamber orchestra and a four-channel electronic element. Petit gave his full confidence to the composer, imposing no narrative or form on the piece. As a result, *Kraanerg* is more of a fully-fledged concert work than Xenakis's other incidental stage music like *Oresteia* or *Medea*, from which concert suites had to be extracted.

Xenakis created the title, a composite word in Greek meaning "to perfect/accomplish" and "[cerebral] energy." While the music is highly abstract, the composer extended the personal struggle to overcome obstacles (in intellectual or creative pursuits) to the global struggles of population and environment, with particular inspiration taken from the social unrest of the time (Harley 2004, 61). He would no doubt have been recalling his own earlier activities as a resistance fighter in Athens in the 1940s.

The chamber orchestra Xenakis had to work with was divided into five woodwinds (piccolo, oboe, Eb clarinet, contrabass clarinet, contrabassoon), six brass (two horns, two trumpets, two trombones), and twelve strings (six violins, two violas, two cellos, two double basses). The tape part was made up of recordings of this same chamber orchestra treated in the studio and mixed across four channels intended to surround the audience. This studio-produced component was particularly desired by the National Arts Centre in Ottawa in order to show off the state-of-the-art technical capabilities of the new venue. The length of the work, far exceeding the capacity of a single roll of audio tape, ensured that there would either need to be two four-track recorders onsite or else that there would be a break to change the tapes (Xenakis foresaw the need to change tapes in his sketches, without building this into the organization of the music. The stage design, carried out by noted op-art figure Victor Vasarely, would have highlighted the staging and lighting capabilities of the theatre as well.

Formal outline

While the music for *Kraanerg* unfolds continuously, it is organized in blocks of clearly delineated material, sounding in succession with occasional overlapping or superpositioning of blocks. The use of silence, between blocks and occasionally within, is also significant to the temporal organization and perceptual experience of the work. These segments of music are primarily distinguished by instrumentation and sonic entity. The ensemble is most often divided into winds and strings, with the winds sometimes further subdivided into woodwinds and brass. Other elements such as register, dynamics, mode of articulation, and density of activity are also important in delineating the blocks of material.

For the listener, the most obvious distinction between sections is the shift between ensemble and tape. One's perception shifts from the stage to the loudspeakers and back again. On this basis, it is possible to chart the formal outline as the alternation of ensemble and tape (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. *Kraanerg*: chart of formal outline showing alternation of onstage musicians and studio-produced tape material. Roman numerals indicate a tripartite overall form on the basis of predominance of one element over the other or a balance between the two. The "choreography" annotations show the succession of movements (with break for intermission) imposed on the music by choreographer Roland Petit for the original presentation.

At this primary level of analysis, 39 segments of music can be distinguished, ranging in duration from 10 to 502 seconds. Interestingly, silences almost always occur in the midst of ensemble sections, inviting consideration of this entity as an active agent rather than an accentuation for shifting from one element to the other (there are actually only two silences between tape and orchestra, occurring in minutes 58-59). There is no linear progression of block durations (although the longest segments do occur in the tape-part segments toward the end), but the relative presence of each entity shifts over time, so that it is possible to discern three divisions in the overall form: Part I (0'00"–23'00") is relatively balanced between orchestra and tape; Part II (23'00"–52'00") is predominantly orchestral; and Part III (52'00"–75'11") is predominantly tape.

This, however, is an overly simplistic analysis of the formal outline of *Kraanerg*. The deployment of instrumental groups (woodwinds/brass, strings) is also important, and there are similar shifts of global timbre in the tape part. Other factors are important as well, helping to further articulate the mosaic-like design.

Compositional elements

In the sketches for *Kraanerg*, there is a listing of elements to be used, along with the definition of sets of “values” for each element. These details from the sketch are summarized as follows:

1. Timbres (instruments, instrumental groupings):
 - Winds (woodwinds, brass)
 - Strings
 - Tape (recorded and studio-processed winds and strings)
2. Register:
 - Extremely high, high, medium, low, extremely low
3. Sound quality/articulation:
 - Ordinario (no vibrato), quilisma (slow, irregular oscillations of pitch), trill, flutter-tongue/tremolo, staccato (repeated)
4. Dynamic level:
 - ppp, pp, p, f, ff, fff*
5. Density:
 - Number of instruments
6. Texture:
 - Glissandi, mixed, clouds, static

This sketch is dated from September 1968, very early in the compositional process. It is evident from later sketches that Xenakis did not implement a rigorous group-theory model to work from for *Kraanerg*. The basic idea, however, of a musical form crafted from a succession of segments of material delineated by particular values of a limited set of parameters (such as the six listed above), is very much at the core of this ambitious work.

Details of the mosaic

Given the information provided by the preliminary sketch listing the compositional elements, it ought to be possible to attempt an analysis of the score on the basis of these given parameters, at least as a point of departure.

Segment 1	38"		
	10"	12"	16"
Timbre	ww/br		
Register	low-med-high		+ex. high
Articulation	stacc.	ord.	stacc.
Dynamics	<i>fff</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>fff</i>
Density	5 ww + 6 br		
Texture	static	(static)	mixed

Table 1. *Kraanerg*: Analysis of Segment 1 of the score using compositional elements as the criteria.

Table 1 summarizes the opening segment of the score. One detail not conveyed there is that the shift in articulation from repeated staccato to normal held notes is staggered across the instruments, to create a gradual transition. Similarly the shift back to staccato is gradual, the entire ensemble not settling on the staccato until the last bar of the segment (two seconds). In the third sub-segment, the piccolo adds a unique element to the overall sonority, articulating a series of short, accented notes in the extreme high register. In the second sub-segment, the texture remains static, but less so, and each instrument changes pitch with the shift to normal articulation. The third sub-segment has more pitch movement, but also retains an aspect of the static texture through repeating the staccato notes. There is a subtlety and attention to details of the musical structure here that points beyond the direct application of the group-theoretical techniques toward creative intervention/invention.

Pitch organization has so far been ignored. Sketches indicate that Xenakis was thinking of pitch in terms of sieve theory, first used extensively for *Nomos alpha*, but rigorous application of this technique does not appear to have been followed. Quarter tones are applied throughout the piece, and could conceivably have been derived from sieve-generated pitch collections (as in *Nomos alpha*), but there are also numerous passages where the strings play natural harmonics, drawing on an obviously limited pitch collection that derives from the acoustical properties of the instruments and not from an algebraic formulation.

The tape-part segments are organized in similar fashion to the orchestral segments. Segment 2 begins four seconds before the end of Segment 1, so that when the live instruments stop the recorded sounds are already present. The segment ends with a similar overlap of four seconds into Segment 3, which returns to the live ensemble, this time introducing the ensemble of strings.

Segment 2	138"								
	16"	7"	19"	19"	6"	7"	44"	5"	15"
Timbre	br		br+str		br	br+str		str	
Register	med		med-hi		med	med-hi		hi	
Articulation	stacc	ord	ord-harm	ord-ord	stacc	ord-harm	ord-ord	ord	batt
Dynamics	variable								
Density	6 br		+ upper str		6 br	+ upper str		upper str	
Texture	static			+gliss	static		+gliss	gliss	clouds

Table 2. *Kraanerg*: Analysis of Segment 2 using compositional elements as the criteria.

It is more challenging to provide a precise analysis of the tape segments, for a number of reasons. For one, the studio processing of the instrumental sounds—which appear to include filtering, amplitude adjustment/distortion, reverberation—makes identification of specific instruments within ensembles of in this case brass and strings difficult. The distribution of the material across the four tracks of the tape complicates the overall texture, even while the tracks share material, and the spatialization really should be considered as a separate compositional element. Isolation of individual tracks makes apparent the presence of both brass and strings throughout the entire segment, but at times the amplitude of the one or the other is so low and limited to one or two track as to hide its presence. The massed string harmonics constitutes a distinct entity within the “sound quality/articulation” category, as do string pizzicato and “col legno battuto,” even though Xenakis did not list these in his sketch. It is also difficult to judge dynamics, as the studio treatment can mask or heighten the effect of particular levels as performed by the musicians for the recording. Nonetheless, shifts of dynamic level are an important factor in articulating sub-segments.

The opening of Segment 2 in some ways sounds very similar to the opening of Segment 1, being based on staccato repeated notes that then shift to held notes. The main differences are that the tape segment uses only brass rather than the full complement of winds, and the studio processing, along with diffusion through a four-channel sound system, alters both the sounds themselves and the listener’s perception of them by means of amplification and spatialization. The segment goes on to differentiate itself by adding the string material (prefiguring the introduction of the live strings in the following segment), and by extending the duration of the passage quite significantly. Relationships on many levels are established in these opening segments that continue to play out over the course of the entire work. While the music itself goes beyond the materials listed in his sketch, Xenakis nonetheless cycles around a limited collection of sonic entities, varied by shifting parameters such as register, dynamics, density, etc.

The structural use of silence

The basic formal outline provided in Figure 3 highlights the incorporation of silence in *Kraanerg*. Indeed, there are nineteen moments of silence altogether, ranging in duration from 1 to 28 seconds. Seventeen of them occur in Part II, the 29-minute section of the work that features the live ensemble predominantly.

As an example of how the silence is treated compositionally, Part II opens at 23’00” with a 38-

second segment for strings alone, playing relatively static bowed natural harmonics, at the highest dynamic level (*fff*) with distributed accents. The music is cut abruptly by a 28-second silence. The strings start in again, at 24'06", this time playing high-density mixed textures of glissandi, pizzicati, battuto, harmonics, trills, etc. This segment lasts for 30 seconds, then is cut by a silence of 4 seconds. The strings return to a more static texture, but sounding regular notes in the middle registers rather than the high harmonics of the earlier segment. This 18-second segment is again interrupted by silence, this time lasting for 16 seconds. After the three segments for strings, the winds enter with a segment that shifts from staccato repeated notes (recalling the opening of the work) to held tones performed as flutter-tongue. With one measure of overlap the strings enter, returning to the held tones of the previous segment. After 14 seconds, the silence cuts in again, lasting for 20 seconds. After that, the winds and strings play off against one another over an extended passage that lasts over three minutes.

In this passage, from 23'00" to 26'00", silence takes up 58 seconds, almost one-third of the total duration. The silences are clearly intended to be heard as equal elements to the sounding ones. They serve no traditional cadential purpose here. Instead, the passage of time is articulated by the playing off of segments, sounding and silent, of changing duration.

Conclusion

The music of *Kraanerg* does not evolve, in a linear, developmental way, from beginning to end. Instead, it proceeds by segment, each one defined by instrumentation, texture, density (of sound as well as degree of activity), register, dynamics, and sound quality. The unpredictable variation of any of these elements alters the material enough to retain our interest. A passage of quilisma (a narrow, sliding line) for the full complement of winds, for example, could create a dense, teeming texture, but a solo Eb clarinet performing the same material results in a perceivable melody (c.f., 34'21", and 34'42"). At the same time, this limited set of elements helps to bind the segments into one larger form, as connections can be perceived across long spans of time. The varying durations of the mosaic-segments and the shifting balance between the global timbral elements add integrity and depth to the structure.

A mosaic is not necessarily nonlinear. Indeed, many—perhaps most—are pictorial, even conveying a narrative. But, with a long experience working with stochastics, embracing the unpredictable as a fundamental aspect of his music, Xenakis sought complexity in his deterministic compositional techniques based on group theory. The nonlinear deployment in time of specific sonic entities and parametrical elements would become for him a basic strategy of his compositional thinking, even when he was not rigorously applying the rules of his theory (Harley 1996). *Kraanerg* is one of the earliest works, and the most substantial, to exemplify Xenakis's nonlinear, mosaic-like approach to composition.

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